

Tracking wheat yellow rust: near real-time data sharing with Nextstrain

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Abstract

Puccinia striiformis f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*) is the causative agent of wheat yellow rust disease, affecting wheat production worldwide. In order to effectively manage this disease, it is important to monitor the genotypes present through surveillance programs. Additionally, the use of public, open source tools such as the Nextstrain toolkit allow for rapid and efficient sharing of data from surveillance programmes. Here we present a Nextstrain instance for *Pst*, which will be a valuable resource for understanding and tracking the distribution of specific genotypes of this important pathogen.

Introduction

Puccinia striiformis f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*) is a fungal pathogen which is the causative agent of wheat yellow (stripe) rust disease. This disease is a key threat to the security of wheat production worldwide and the geography of outbreaks has recently expanded, particularly since 2000 (Beddow et al., 2015). Due to the obligate biotrophic nature of this pathogen, isolation and multiplication of individual strains for genetic and pathological research is technically difficult and time-consuming. To address this and provide rapid genotypic data for *Pst* isolates the 'field pathogenomics' approach was developed. This method utilises *Pst*-infected plant tissue that is sampled directly in the field and subsequently subjected to RNA-seq analysis. This high-resolution approach enables *Pst* isolates to be classified into genetic groups, which has been shown to tightly correlate with their associated virulence profiles (Hubbard et al., 2015). Building on this methodology, the recent development of the Mobile and Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) platform in addition uses portable sequencing technologies to provide strain-level diagnostics for *Pst* (Radhakrishnan et al., 2019). Utilising amplicon sequencing of a highly variable *Pst* gene set, MARPLE diagnostics can genotypically define strains, for the first time, in just 48 hours directly from *Pst*-infected plant tissue. This also provides a small, unified dataset that can then be readily explored using analytic and visualisation tools

previously created for smaller bacterial and viral genomic datasets such as the Nextstrain toolkit.

Nextstrain is an open source toolkit for the analysis and open sharing of data on pathogen outbreaks. This software was initially built to study the evolution of viral pathogens of humans and track strain movement in near real-time (Hadfield et al., 2018). Since its initial development, Nextstrain now currently hosts curated instances for ten viral pathogens and one bacterial pathogen of humans, alongside instances for four viral pathogens of humans and one of cassava generated by the community. Nextstrain contains all the tools needed to visualise individual genome sequences of a number of viral or bacterial isolates in a publicly hosted platform. For instance, a recent instance was developed that covers twenty years of the West Nile Virus (WNV) in North America, demonstrating the ability of this toolkit to analyse and share data on historical samples (Hadfield et al., 2019). Furthermore, as COVID-19 progresses across the world, Nextstrain provides all researchers with a platform to monitor genotypic changes and track strain movement in near real-time. Here we present the first use of Nextstrain to analyse a eukaryotic plant pathogen, with samples ranging in isolation date from 2013 to 2018 and sourced from a range of geographical locations worldwide. This publicly available analysis has the potential to aid researchers in future work on the epidemiology and pathogenicity of this organism as well as providing a forum for the public sharing of results from future surveillance operations.

Methods

Preparation of Nextstrain input files

A set of 379 *Pst* isolates were used to establish this Nextstrain instance that were previously described (Hubbard et al., 2015; Milus et al., 2015; Hovmøller et al., 2016; Walter et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2017; Bueno-Sancho et al., 2017; Boshoff et al., 2019; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019). Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were identified as previously described (Hubbard et al., 2015) and consensus sequence files of 242 polymorphic *Pst* genes created (Radhakrishnan et al., 2019). A concatenated file of the consensus sequence of all 379 *Pst* isolates was created with seqkit version 0.9.1 (Shen et al., 2016) and EMBOSS version 6.5.7 (Rice et al., 2000).

Phylogenetic analysis

Phylogenetic analysis was carried out with a maximum likelihood approach using RAxML version 8.0.20 using the GTRGAMMA model with a random seed of 100 (Stamatakis, 2014). In order to improve the legibility of the tree, rerooting was performed to sample ET08/10 with RAxML.

Preparation of files for Nextstrain

The phylogenetic tree created above was further prepared for display in Nextstrain through the use of the augur toolkit within the Nextstrain shell (Hadfield et al., 2018). Firstly, the 'refine' command was used to modify the tree file with information from the metadata file, with the 'keep root' option specified to avoid rerooting of the tree. Following this, the 'traits' command was used to infer ancestral traits from the tree, specifying the host, date, group and collector columns to ensure that these fields were shown in the visualisation. Finally, the export command was used to produce the necessary JSON file for visualisation.

Hosting of files and availability of data

Raw sequencing reads for all *Pst* isolates are available as part of the following BioProjects: PRJEB15280, PRJEB31334, PRJEB33109, PRJNA256347 and PRJNA257181. JSON files used to generate the visualisation and scripts mentioned above are available at <https://github.com/SaundersLab/PST>. The Nextstrain instance is hosted at <https://nextstrain.org/community/saunderslab/PST>.

Results and Discussion

A new instance of Nextstrain for an important crop disease

We present the first use of Nextstrain for a eukaryotic plant pathogen. This demonstrates the potential of this platform for the analysis of an agriculturally important pathogen species and its potential to aid in responses to outbreaks when integrated within disease surveillance programs. Specifically, this instance utilised data generated for establishing the Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics method for the wheat yellow rust pathogen, *Pst*. Incorporating sequence data from just 242 polymorphic genes, this small, unified dataset is ideal for visualisation in the Nextstrain interface, providing a fully open, interactive user environment.

Nextstrain allows for the customisation of the tree view to fit the user's needs

When a user loads the *Pst* Nextstrain instance, the first panel shown contains an interactive phylogenetic tree of the 379 *Pst* isolates used initially for this instance. By default, this is presented as a rectangular tree coloured by genetic group (Figure 1) (Radhakrishnan et al., 2019). However, users can also select different tree visualisation options such as radial and unrooted (Figure 2). Additionally, a user can change the colour of the tree tips such as colour-coding by country or geographic region (Figure 3). The tree can also be magnified to focus on specific clades of interest by clicking on given branches (Figure 4). Finally, individual nodes can be selected to view the associated metadata for a specific sample. In summary, this allows a user to customise the view of the phylogeny to best fit their interest.

Showing 379 of 379 genomes.

Phylogeny

genetic group ^

- PstS7
- Triticale
- PstS10
- PstS8
- PstS1
- PstS4
- France 1988-2013
- UK 1978-2011
- Cluster 3 (Hubbard)
- Other
- PstS2 v27
- PstS5 v17
- PstS6
- PstS9 v17

RESET LAYOUT

Figure 1: The *Pst* Nextstrain instance phylogeny is automatically shown in rectangular format and coloured by genetic group. Once loaded, the Nextstrain instance first displays a tree of the 379 *Pst* isolates initially used. Genetic groups are as previously defined (Hubbard et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019).

A

Showing 379 of 379 genomes.

Phylogeny

genetic group ^

RESET LAYOUT

B

Showing 379 of 379 genomes.

Phylogeny

genetic group ^

RESET LAYOUT

Figure 2: The shape of the Nextstrain tree can be modified according to user preferences. (A) A radial tree with the circular lines representing divergence. (B) An unrooted phylogenetic tree. *Pst* genetics groups are as previously defined (Hubbard et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019).

A

Showing 379 of 379 genomes.

B

Showing 379 of 379 genomes.

Figure 3: Nextstrain also allows users to alter the colour of tree tips. The phylogenetic tree can be modified to highlight groups of *Pst* isolates by different criteria. **(A)** Tree labelled with isolates coloured by country of isolation. **(B)** Tree labelled with isolates coloured by region of isolation.

Showing 100 of 379 genomes.

Phylogeny

genetic group ^

- PstS7
- Triticale
- PstS10
- PstS8
- PstS1
- PstS4
- France 1988-2013
- UK 1978-2011
- Cluster 3 (Hubbard)
- Other
- PstS2 v27
- PstS5 v17
- PstS6
- PstS9 v17

RESET LAYOUT

Figure 4: Users can choose to investigate specific clades of interest through the selection of branches in the tree panel. By selecting a branch on the tree with the mouse, a user can view a subset of samples in greater detail.

Users can customise the map view

The second panel of the Nextstrain instance displays the distribution of samples on a world map (Figure 5). Individual *Pst* isolates can be coloured by genetic group (default), country or geographic region (Figure 6). The selected colour option is then reflected in both the global map and phylogenetic tree. Samples are located on the map by country of isolation and represented by pie charts displaying the proportion of isolates in each genetic group for that country. Alternatively, the precise geographic region or specific location can be shown for each *Pst* isolate (Figure 7). Finally, as tree clades are selected the map automatically adjusts to display only *Pst* isolates within the selected clade (Figure 8). This demonstrates how users can customise the format of the map view.

A subset of isolates can be selected to aid in analyses

As a large number of *Pst* isolates (379) were included in this Nextstrain instance, a user may find it useful to filter in order to analyse a subset of *Pst* isolates. Current filters include: country of isolation (Country), the associated manuscript (author), the recorded variety the *Pst* isolate was identified on (host), the genetic group (Genetic Group) and the identity of the person or organisation who collected the isolate (collector). This filtering modifies both the tree and the map discussed above (Figure 9). This provides flexibility for users to analyse specific subsets of isolates of interest in more detail.

A

Figure 6: Nextstrain allows users to change the colour-coding of *Pst* isolates on the map by selected criteria. The map from the second panel of the Nextstrain instance can be modified to colour the selection of *Pst* isolates by different criteria. (A) Map labelled with isolates coloured by country of isolation. (B) Map labelled with isolates coloured by region of isolation.

A

Figure 7: The Nextstrain map enables users to alter the grouping of *Pst* isolates. The map from the second panel of the Nextstrain instance can be modified to group the selection of *Pst* isolates by different criteria. All isolates are coloured by genetic group (Hubbard et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019). **(A)** Map labelled with isolates grouped by the location of isolation. **(B)** Map labelled with isolates grouped by region of isolation.

Figure 8: A user can choose to investigate a specific genetic group of *Pst* isolates of interest by filtering the selection. This example shows the map after filtering to show only isolates of genetic group PstS10 (Hubbard et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019).

A

Filter by country

Austria (2) Azerbaijan (2) Belgium (4) Bulgaria (1) Canada (6) Chile (5) China (33) Croatia (2) Czechia (4) Denmark (3) Ethiopia (66) France (24) Germany (23) Italy (2) Kenya (1) Lesotho (1) New Zealand (4) Pakistan (6) Poland (6) Romania (1) Serbia (1) Slovakia (2) South Africa (9) Spain (1) Sweden (12) Turkey (1) UK (111) USA (40) Uzbekistan (3) Zimbabwe (3)

Filter by author

Ali et al., 2017 B (5) Boshoff et al., 2019 B (11) Bueno-Sancho et al., 2017 B (137) Hovmøller et al., 2016 A (4) Hubbard et al., 2015 B (63) Milus et al., 2015 (1) Radhakrishnan et al., 2019 B (155) Walter et al., 2016 B (3)

Filter by host

2141 (1) 555012 (1) AC Barrie (3) Akteur (5) Alixan (1) Allez-Y (1) Altigo (1) Ambition (3) Arkadia (1) Artdeco (1) Audace (1) BOLO (1) Belvoir (1) Bergoumo (1) Bonneville (1) Breeding Line (1) Brock (1) Bulala (1) Byrd (1) Claire (4) Cocoon (1) Contur (1) Cordiale (2) Crusoe (1) DH13SRW024-182 (1) Dandaa (2) Dashen (1) Decade (1) Deloris (1) Digalu (4) Dure (1) ET13-A2 (2) Enkoy (1) Enola (1) Everest (1) Expert (1) Express (1) Fairplay (1) Fito 1404-15 (1) Fito 1401-87 cv. Pantera (1) GYT3-190 DN (1) Galama (1) Galian (1) Glasgow (1) HY2042 (1) HY2047 (1) Henkolo (1) Hereford (1) Hermann (1) Hidase (2) Hoggana (2) Horatio (1) Huluka (1) Hysun (1) Irnerio (1) JB Asano (7) JB Diego (1) Jorvik (1) K505hw14 (1) K62954A (1) KBG-01 (1) KWS Dali (1) KWS Kielder (4) KWS Magic (1) KWS Rowan (1) KWS Santiago (2) KWS Sterling (3) KWS196 (1) Kannlark (1) Karur (1) Kasuku (1) Kekeba (1) Kingbird (1) Kobra (1) Kometus (4) Kranich (6) Kubsu (2) LCS 2141 (1) LCS Compass (1) LCS Jet (1) LGW56 (Panacea) (1) LGW65 (Energise) (1) Laurier (1) Legenda (1) Lemu (1) Line (1) Linus (1) Linz (2) Loft (1) Madda Wolabu (3) Massari (1) Millenium (2) Morocco FF-B (1) Morph (1) NC13142-33 (1) NC13142-35 (1) NC13142-36 (1) NIC08-108 (1) Norin (1) ORCF 101R (1) Oakley (11) Ogoicho (1) Onix (2) Opal (1) Otto (1) Ovation (1) PBW343(SC) (1) PS 279 (1) Panacea (1) Panorama (1) Pavon-76 (1) Penhold (1) Perennial grass (1) Primus (1) Princeps (1) RW41088 (1) ReR04 (1) ReR110 (1) ReR138 (1) ReR22 (1) ReR32 (1) ReR64 (1) Recital (1) Relay (2) Ritmo (1) Robigus (3) Rosario (1) Ruby Lee (1) Rye (2) SPPSN#15 (1) Sanate (1) Sax (2) Scout (1) Seedway (1) Sisson (1) Snowmass (1) Sofumer (3) Solstice (11) Sy Epton (1) Taita (1) Tam 112 (1) Target (1) Tilman (1) Timber (1) Toisandor (1) Torch (3) Trapez (2) Trigo camargo (1) Triticale Amarillo (1) Triticale Bennette (1) Triticale Fido (1) Triticale Orleac (1) Triticale Phidahlia (1) Triticale Ragtac (1) Triticale Tarzan (1) Turandot Baryton cross (1) Unknown Durum Wheat (1) Unknown Emmer Wheat (1) Unknown Spreader (1) Unknown Triticale (3) Victo (5) Vuka (3) Wane (1) Warrior (4) YS 221 (1) Yellowstone (1) Yr31 (1)

Filter by genetic group

Cluster 3 (Hubbard et al., 2015) (9) France 1988-2013 (8) Other (171) PstS1 (1) PstS10 (101) PstS2 v27 (2) PstS4 (1) PstS5 v17 (2) PstS6 (1) PstS7 (36) PstS8 (15) PstS9 v17 (1) Triticale (15) UK 1978-2011 (16)

Filter by collector

A. Resweber (5) Alison Bentley (1) Amelia Hubbard (6) Andrea Hanková (2) Ayele and Bekele (4) Bazelaine (1) Briard (1) Clare Lewis (1) Claude Pope (1) Dario (3) Dave Hodson (11) Dave, Ayele and Yoseph (9) Dave, Gebre, Yoseph (2) Dave, gebre and yoseph (6) Dave, gebre, yoseph (1) Driecus Lesch (2) Fikirte Yirga (15) Fikirte, Tsega-ab, Yoseph (3) Fikirte, tsega, yoseph (3) Grellier (3) Hamon (2) Harpinder S. Randhawa (6) J P Legoff (4) J-C Talbourdet (3) James Brown (1) Jay Kalous (2) Jeron Chatelain (2) Kulumsa (4) Marcin Lanski (2) Marco Martelli (1) Marla Barnett (7) Novosevovie (1) Pedro Liberal (1) Prochnow (9) Prochnow: Rosie Bryson (9) Ricardo Madariaga Burrows (5) Richard Oliver (4) Rosemary Bayles (3) Ruth Bryant (4) Suomeng Song (3) Susanne Kirchmaier (2) Szymon Łączny (2) Szymon Łączny (1) Tina Henriksen (3) Tina Henriksson (7) Todor Manslov (1) Tracy Richards (4) Vaclav Sklenar (1) Viktor (2) Willem Boshoff (11) Xianming Cheng (24) Yves Decroos (4) Zofia Banaszak (1)

Filter by region

africa (80) asia (45) europe (199) north america (46) oceania (4) south america (3)

B

C

Figure 9: A demonstration of filtering *Pst* isolates by a variety of metadata fields. Five different filter categories are currently available in this Nextstrain instance: country of isolation, manuscript in which the isolate was first published, the host variety on which the isolate was found, the genetic group assignment of the isolate (Hubbard et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2019) and the identity of the collector. **(A)** The filters as displayed in the Nextstrain instance with genetic group PstS10 selected. **(B)** An image of the phylogenetic tree after filtering for *Pst* genetic group PstS10. **(C)** An image of the map after filtering for genetic group PstS10.

Conclusions

In this work we have demonstrated the use of the open source Nextstrain interface for the analysis of both a eukaryote and a plant pathogen. This instance was built using data from a set of 242 highly polymorphic *Pst* genes used in the MARPLE diagnostics platform. As such, there is scope for this instance to be kept up-to-date as *Pst*-infected plant samples are analysed using this methodology. This resource will likely prove a valuable tool for tracking the distribution of *Pst* genotypes on a global scale into the future as such genomics-based methodology is adopted more widely within surveillance programs.

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